

WAYS OF DEVELOPING LISTENING SKILLS OF ENGLISH
LEARNERS

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Abstract: Language is a main tool of communication and it is confirmed as a connection of human being. However, communication does not include only speaking, but also listening that is the way to understand and feel how the conversation or relationships going on. According to statistics, almost billion people use English as a communicative language on a daily life and it has already entered to every field of the society. This paper aims to clarify the importance of receptive skills as well as focus highly on some productive methods for teaching them.

Keywords: receptive, teacher, classroom, learner, methods and strategies.

It is obvious that, language is a weapon in communicating human's ideas, thoughts and feelings to other fellow human beings. To learn a language, people are required to study the skills of that particular one. The main thing is to learn a foreign or second language such as English also, the learners have to learn all four skills of it to prove themselves as good communicators. These four skills are divided into two categories, which are, receptive or passive skills and productive or active skills. Listening and reading are receptive skills where the learners just receive and understand these skills and there is no need for the learners to produce language to do these. On the other hand, speaking and writing skills are productive skills here learners have to produce language utilizing these skills. But the main factor which is generalized of them is accuracy that is really important. None of them should be neglectful and pay less attention than one another. Among these four skills, listening is the first skill. According to Hornby (2005) the act of listening means,

“ To pay attention to somebody/something that you can hear”. But there is a difference between listening and hearing. Hearing refers to the sounds that your ears receive and it is a physical process that provided a person do not have any hearing problems. By contrast listening requires more than that, it requires focus and concentrated effort, both mental and somehow physical. There are some learners that opt for more listening than speaking who are called good listeners.

As Dr. Rachel Naomi Remen mentioned “ The most basic and powerful way to connect to another person is listening. Just listen. Perhaps the most important thing we ever give each attention.”

In fact, schooling aims to bring up multilateral perfect generation for the future life.

And language classes involve teachers and pupils. Both types of people purpose to learn foreign language and actually for evolving listening comprehension. According to research, at least 45% of that time is spent listening. In schools, students spend 60 – 70 % of their classroom time listening. They assist students to develop a set of listening strategies and match appropriate strategies to each listening situation. In the following main types of listening activities ought to be clarified:

1. Pre-listening activities. They are called also introductory activities that is an introduction to the topic of the text and activities focusing on the language of the context. They aim to deal eith all of these issue which are generating interest, building self – confidence and facilitating comprehension.

2. While – listening activities. In these activities learner receives a series of comprehension activities for developing listening skills and teachers propose to practice listening subskills. In that time a learners has a chance to confirm his or her prediction about the text.

3. Post – listening activities. Last stage is post – listening one which requests learners to talk about how a topic in the text relates to their own lives or give their opinions on parts of the text. These activities have a goal to utilize the knowledge

gained from listening and summarize the ideas. It also includes, working with mistakes which part is more difficult than other parts learners made them.

They might be used distinctively by teachers by the help of information technologies, audio materials of radio programs, online podcasts, instructional lectures and other audio messages. Educators ought to model this interactive listening process in class with learners, and then instruct them to repeat the exercise on their own. First, teacher instructs students to prepare for listening by considering anything that they will intent to learn from the content of the audio. Once they have written down or shared these ideas, then play the audio material, allowing the students to take notes if helpful.

Moreover, another helpful resource for teaching listening skills are video tools, including short sketches, news programs, documentary films, interview segments, and dramatic and comedic material. As with audio materials, it is important to choose the portion and length of the video materials in accordance with the skill level of students. Firstly, students watch the video without any sound and discuss it together. In this time teacher should encourage the students to identify what they think will be the content of the tool. Then, they watch the video material again, this time with sound, allowing students to take notes if helpful for their skill level. After the completion of the video, educator can have students write a brief summary of the video, or it is possible to take time discuss as a group how the video compares with the students' expectations.

CONCLUSION

By the way of conclusion, it is apparent from this paper that, since listening is really essential to be a good listener and perfect communicator, lessons should be encompassed, while post listening activities which are important steps for both teachers and pupils. Besides that, it is incredible to exploit some instructional and interesting methods connected with authenticity to introduce real native speech.

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